

D5.1 COMMUNICATION, MARKETING & STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

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Author(s)	Sara Pittonet, Sara Garavelli, Marieke Willems, Silvana Muscella (Trust-IT Services)
Abstract	This document outlines the strategy for communicating RDA Europe 4.0 efficiently and to ensure an effective engagement of project stakeholders. KPIs for monitoring marketing and communication activities and outcomes of engagement activities are also documented.

Dissemination Level

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Author(s)	Sara Pittonet, Sara Garavelli, Marieke Willems Silvana Muscella (Trust-IT Services)
Editor(s)	
Contributor(s)	
Reviewer(s)	Natalie Harrower (RIA), Sarah Jones (UEDIN)
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Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DMS	Document Management System
DoA	Description of Action
DRI	Digital Repository of Ireland
DSM	Digital Single Market
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GB	Governing Board
ICT	Information & Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project Coordinator
R&I	Research & Innovation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RIA	Royal Irish Academy
TRUST-IT	Trust-IT Services
UEDIN	University of Edinburgh
UGOE	University of Göttingen
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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1 Executive Summary

Consistent and content-rich communication is strategic to showcasing the results and impact of the objectives and goals within RDA Europe 4.0. As the project involves considering global RDA guiding principles, this report ensures that the efforts in place, in the European plan, work in synergy with this overarching objective. All of the results that the project aims to attain require a thoroughly detailed dissemination plan for Europe, which calls for both physical and online engagement. This plan presents the activities to be put in place by the consortium during the 27 months of the project. This plan has been built on a series of communication and promotional campaigns for the main RDA Europe assets, primarily: RDA Outputs and recommendations, the financial support offered to Europeans through the cascading grant system, the evolution and delivery of the established and new National node Networks, the opportunities for individuals and the events and webinars organised within the project timeframe.

Four (4) different communication and promotional campaigns are presented in this plan, listed below, with detailed timelines presenting the activities that will be put in place. These campaigns and timelines will be followed throughout the project lifetime to ensure that RDA Europe 4.0's mission and vision is spread to the target audience through traditional, online and social communication and marketing activities, with the aim of ensuring proper engagement, uptake and visibility of RDA Europe 4.0 results.

Section 2 of the plan presents, the project **Communication, marketing and stakeholder engagement strategy**, including the project objectives and the communication campaigns that will support them. **Section 3** illustrates the **RDA Europe value proposition and assets**, while **section 4** guides the reader through **RDA Europe 4.0 Outreach & Communication campaigns**, with visual timelines and detailed lists of activities:

1. Communication and promotion of RDA Outputs
2. Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network
3. Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals
4. RDA Europe Events & webinars.

Section 5 is dedicated to the **RDA Europe Stakeholders Analysis, communication strategy and plans**. This outlines the clear objectives and expectations for the target audiences identified for RDA Europe 4.0 and namely: individuals and organisations working in the overall data management framework; projects and initiatives in the context of the EOSC; policy makers and funding bodies to look to the future sustainability of RDA in Europe and abroad.

Section 6 offers insights on the **Communication and Engagement tools** and channels to be used to make the plan as pragmatic as possible, including branding, online presence and content production, collaterals and social media channel utilisation and distribution.

Finally, **section 7** states how **Internal communication** is maintained, considering RDA's complex structure and workings, among all of the communication actors in RDA Europe 4.0 project to ensure effective engagement with all project partners.

2 Communication, marketing and stakeholder engagement strategy

The RDA Europe 4.0 communication, marketing & stakeholder engagement strategy has a twofold objective: on the one hand, to maximise the visibility and ensuring uptake of the outputs of RDA - the Research Data Alliance, on the other, to ensure engagement of and contribution by European stakeholders via a series of cascading grant programmes and beyond.

The specific objectives of the entire communication, marketing and stakeholder engagement strategy are summarised in Table 1:

Specific Objectives:	Main targeted activities	Comms campaign
OBJ1 Developing & implementing a 27-month pragmatic and user-oriented communication & outreach strategy to raise awareness of RDA results (recommendations, outputs, ICT technical specifications) and stimulate their uptake	Promotion of the RDA results and related adoption stories; Adoption grants; Establishment of collaborations with EU initiatives and ESFRI projects willing to adopt/contribute to the RDA outputs; Monitoring the adoption of RDA ICT Technical Specifications in public procurement; Promotion and support to RDA global in the organisation of 5 RDA plenaries; Publication of RDA outputs in the CODATA journals; Webinars to promote the benefits in adopting a specific RDA output.	RDA Europe promotion of RDA Outputs RDA Europe Events & webinars
OBJ2 Stimulating the participation of European individuals into RDA	Promotion of the RDA value proposition for individuals; Targeted advertising of open calls for early careers, experts, ambassadors; Promotion and support to RDA global in the organisation of 5 RDA plenaries; Webinars for RDA newcomers; Webinars to promote the opportunities for individuals at national level.	Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals RDA Europe Events & webinars

Specific Objectives:	Main targeted activities	Comms campaign
<p>OBJ3 Supporting the engagement of European organisations, including industry and national/European research funding bodies, into RDA</p>	<p>Promotion of the RDA value proposition for organisations; Targeted advertising of open calls for new nodes; Support of the node stakeholder engagement activities at national level; Targeted communication around the new European organisations joining the Organisational Assembly; Promotion and support to RDA global in the organisation of 5 RDA plenaries; Organisation of workshops targeting industry, including SMEs; Participation to policy events at European and national level.</p>	<p>Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network RDA Europe Events & webinars</p>
<p>OBJ4 Supporting the on-boarding of new communities into RDA</p>	<p>Targeted advertising of open calls for ambassadors; Continuous country-based messaging via the network of nodes to grow membership; Promotion and support to RDA global in the organisation of 5 RDA plenaries; Production of targeted discipline-specific RDA promotional material.</p>	<p>Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals RDA Europe Events & webinars</p>
<p>OBJ5 Educating stakeholders on the impact RDA and its results could have on the society at large and on the European Open Science strategy</p>	<p>Delivering a comprehensive RDA Europe 4.0 Impact analysis considering support, node based, and global RDA activities; Highlighting how RDA can contribute to Open Science in Europe and to the latest EU policy data-related movements (e.g. EOSC, FAIR data movement)</p>	<p>RDA Europe promotion of RDA Outputs RDA Europe Events & webinars</p>

Specific Objectives:	Main targeted activities	Comms campaign
OBJ6 Ensure coordinated communication & synergies between RDA Europe 4.0 & RDA global	Active participation into the RDA Secretariat; Promotion of RDA Europe 4.0 activities within the RDA global communications and vice versa; Promotion and support to RDA global in the organisation of 5 RDA plenaries; Regular meetings and synchronisation activities.	All campaigns in synchronisation with D4.1 (See D4.1 <i>Updated RDA Communication Strategy</i>)

Table 1: RDA Europe 4.0 communication, marketing and stakeholder engagement specific objectives

3 RDA Europe value proposition and assets

The RDA Europe strengths and unique “selling” points are summarised below¹. These points will be the focus of the RDA Europe 4.0 communication, marketing and engagement strategy.

1. **European contribution to the RDA Community: human network and neutral platform:** Over the years the community of RDA has built a strong, global, bottom-up, multifaceted human network composed of all different stakeholders around data sharing and interoperability, from data experts and practitioners to policy makers and funders. RDA has become the neutral place where anyone can create a group, and where a series of actions can take place. These range from discussions, comments and decisions on social and technical aspects about data sharing, exchange, and interoperability, to problem-solving infrastructure environments, services or software to be endorsed and used by individuals, projects and organisations., based upon and also acting as open standards. Over 50% of RDA members are from Europe: stimulating and increasing the participation of European individuals and organisations into RDA is therefore at the core of the European engagement strategy.
2. **RDA Recommendations and Outputs and EU ICT technical specifications:** The RDA Outputs are the technical and social infrastructure solutions developed by the RDA Working Groups or Interest Groups that enable data sharing, exchange, and interoperability. The RDA outputs span from the flagship RDA-endorsed adoptable recommendations to other non-endorsed outputs like white papers, guidelines and reports. Many of these outputs and recommendations have been created or adopted by European members/organisations. Furthermore, RDA Europe over the years has promoted several recommendations to be recognised as ICT technical specifications by the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform (MSP) on ICT standardisation. Some of them are already part of public procurement procedures. In Europe a quite intense effort is being dedicated to ensure uptake of RDA recommendations and outputs by the community. The activities performed and planned by European teams, such as the identification and promotion of adoption stories as well as the outreach plan under definition in collaboration with the RDA Secretariat, can be considered best practices to follow as part of a much broader outreach plan for the benefit of the worldwide RDA community.
3. **Services from RDA outputs:** RDA recommendations, besides specifications, can be data models, schemas, ontologies, certifications, registries, workflows or even software. There are cases where related services, tools or models have been developed as part of the RDA outputs. The effort done by European research teams in this sense, in collaboration with worldwide teams, will be subject to special promotion in the Region.
4. **Cascading grants.** To increase the European contribution and uptake of RDA results across all scientific domains and types of organisations, RDA Europe 4.0 is offering financial support to individuals and organisations via a cascading grant mechanism. RDA Europe grants are available for new RDA Europe nodes, early career researchers and experts, RDA ambassadors, and RDA output-adoption cases.
5. **RDA Europe Nodes Network:** Single organisations, or groups of organisations, representing one or more countries, committed to support research data policies at national or regional level, promoting research data management best practices and solutions in Europe and actively engaged in RDA. The RDA Europe project offers grant funding to establish nodes and ongoing support to engage stakeholders from the region.
6. **RDA Europe Events & webinars:** Since its onset, the RDA plenary meetings have been an important asset for RDA. Bringing together the RDA international community, the plenaries have supported the production of RDA results, facilitated international cooperation and fostered the

¹ Some of these selling points had been identified by RDA Europe Task Force on Sustainability and included in the Final Report, February 2018.

networking that is central to bridging social and technical barriers. RDA Europe supports the organisation of 5 plenaries over the duration of the project, whilst financially supporting two of them in Europe. In addition to the plenaries, many other events will also make up the RDA Europe workplan such as national/regional node workshops, industry events, discipline-focused events, topic-specific events (e.g. a forum dedicated to GDPR) and the organisation of targeted webinars to highlight and record experiences and promote best practices in RDA.

For each of these assets specific communication and outreach campaigns will be put in place. Stakeholders, activities and KPIs related to these campaigns are detailed in the next chapters.

4 RDA Europe 4.0 Outreach & Communication campaigns

This chapter describes the different promotional campaigns that will be performed by RDA Europe 4.0 covering a one-year period from July 2018 (M5) to July 2019 (M17). At month 18 (April 2019), the plan for the remaining months of the projects will be released (D5.2 Communication, Marketing & Stakeholder Engagement Plan update).

4.1 Communication and promotion of RDA Outputs

RDA Europe 4.0 has a specific mandate to monitor the uptake of RDA outputs and to encourage further uptake, through promotion of the value of the outputs themselves and the value gained by adoption. An effective communication campaign is therefore fundamental to promote the RDA recommendations and outputs to groups and organisations within and outside RDA and further stimulate test, adoption and implementation.

As part of this campaign different actions will be implemented:

- **Informative campaigns on RDA Adoption**, providing information about the benefits gained by research teams, with the aim to encourage others to use RDA Recommendations and outputs. These campaigns include the production of *news pieces* and *press releases*; the design, creation and distribution of *marketing materials* about RDA outputs and their adoption, including RDA Recommendation cards and Adoption Story factsheets; *newsletters* campaigns to keep the community up-to-date about Recommendations and outputs endorsement and adoption processes; the organisation of *webinars*; *social media distribution* of RDA outputs leveraging on the scientific domains of interest, relevant hashtags, keywords, threads and social media profiles of relevant RDA members. Specific social media *visibility will be ensured to Working Groups* responsible of the release, endorsement and adoption of these outputs.
- **Promotional campaigns for the RDA Outputs Adoption programme**. The cascading grant mechanism will be utilised selectively to provide financial support for testing RDA results and their integration with existing systems and workflows in research. Grants will be given to organizations called to carry out small scale projects to demonstrate take-up of RDA's outputs and ICT Technical Specifications. One unique wave will be launched later in 2018 (October and open until December 2018). As per all the other campaigns promoting the RDA cascading grants, specific activities will be put in place to *promote the launch of the calls (call launch campaigns)*, to inform about relevant deadlines and requirements (*call closure campaigns*), and to *ensure visibility to the awarded individuals* and organizations. In addition, special visibility will be given to the *report on the results* of mapping and monitoring exercise to be fed back to relevant RDA governing bodies to allow to understand more clearly whether factors can be identified that support or inhibit adoption, and how recognition of those factors can inform future RDA work (these are detailed in the following deliverables: D2.3 and D2.4).
- **Promotion of 4 special collections in the CODATA data Science Journal** showcasing the RDA outputs & uses cases. As part of the activities led by the Italian Node (CNR), four calls for papers for the [Data Science Journal special collection](#) will be launched to give visibility to high quality papers describing the latest results of RDA working groups (WGs) or interest groups (IGs), including recommendation and associated use cases that could highlight the added value of RDA work in the data related fields. As part of this plan, specific activities will support promotion of the calls and will ensure visibility to the accepted articles. These articles will also feed into the information and training campaigns mentioned above to contribute, for instance, to the creation of new Adoption stories.
- **Awareness creation and monitoring of adoption of the RDA Europe ICT Technical Specifications**. New materials such as a *specific line of RDA Recommendation Cards*, a *flyer* and a *timeline explaining the necessary steps to be recognised as ICT Technical Specifications*, will be produced to support the awareness raising about RDA ICT Technical Specifications in Europe.

- **Establishment of collaborations with EU initiatives and ESFRI projects willing to adopt/contribute to the RDA outputs:** outreach campaign to EU initiatives and ESFRI projects to understand how they can leverage RDA to address the data-related challenges they have and to promote adoption of RDA results. WP3 have devised specific engagement approaches and target activities, tailoring the RDA Europe value proposition to each project / infrastructures needs.
- **Promotion and support to RDA global in the organisation of 5 RDA plenaries:** Specific sessions on RDA outputs/adoption cases and ICT Technical Specifications will be included as part of the programme of the RDA plenaries.

The RDA European and Global Communication teams will support further the collection and dissemination of adoption stories to better disseminate the RDA achievements and the opportunities of using RDA results. A process will be defined within the Global Communication team and aligned with a similar plan to be defined at European level and linked to the RDA Output-Adoption programme.

See D4.1 Updated RDA Communication Strategy for further reference

The visualised planning in the timeline below is a living and co-created document for all WP5 project partners to work on and update from M6-M17 (See Internal Communication processes).

Timeline 1 Communication and promotion of RDA Outputs M6-M17

4.1.1 Campaign detailed activities

Informative and training campaigns on RDA Adoption

Communication activities on RDA Adoption stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Adoption Story / 2 months 1 news piece version of it and 1 video animation / adoption story Continuous Social media campaign 1 overall video about RDA Adoption stories 2 CORDIS Articles per year 2 DSM blog publications per year 1 webinar per year (See RDA Europe Events & webinars)
Communication activities on RDA outcomes, showing the WG/IG behind them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 explanatory, non-technical article / recommendation 1 Quote from WG/ IG / recommendation 1 News item in the RDA monthly newsletters / recommendation 1 RDA Card / (new) Recommendation 1 webinar per year (See RDA Europe Events & webinars) Continuous Social media campaign
Overall project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10 RDA recommendations and outputs implemented in other EU initiatives, including EOSC and ESFRI projects (KPI 3.3) At least 2 adoption stories for each European node

Promotional campaigns for the RDA Outputs Adoption programme

Call launch activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 press release Continuous Social media campaign 1 call infographic
Call closure activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 news piece about call closure Social media campaign to remind the closure deadline
Communication activity to provide visibility to the call results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 press release and 1 online page dedicated to the awarded people 1 White paper leveraging on the report on the results of mapping and monitoring exercise (D2.3 and D2.4, M27)
Overall project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10 new documented Adoption stories focusing on Recommendations & Outputs launched and endorsed during the RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime (KPI2.4)

Promotion of 4 special collections in the CODATA data Science Journal

Communication activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 press release and news piece / each of the call for papers Continuous Social media campaign 1 news piece dedicated to the accepted papers / call edition (4 in total) 6 papers *4 Journal editions turned into Adoption Stories (24 in total)
Overall project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 special editions of CODATA Data Science Journal focusing on RDA outputs and use cases

Visibility to RDA Europe Technical Specifications

Visibility to RDA Europe Technical Specifications

Communication activities	updated slidedeck about RDA Europe Technical Specifications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> infographics about the 4 Specifications recognised so far 1 infographic / new specification
Overall project KPIs	Up to 5 ICT Technical Specifications submitted to EU Multi-stakeholder Platform, considering the portfolio of recognised and endorsed RDA Recommendations and their relevance/applicability as ICT Technical Specifications.

Social media KPIs

<i>These KPIs relate to all promotional campaigns (as described in chapters 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4)</i>	5,000+ overall social media followers – LinkedIn & Twitter [M24]; 10,000+ by end of Project [M27] (KPI 5.5)
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Table 2 Communication and promotion of RDA Outputs detailed activities

4.2 Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network

RDA Europe established a network of nine national nodes to foster adoption of RDA outputs in the European region. The initial node network will be expanded over the lifetime of the project through three open calls for new nodes to achieve a total of 22 national/regional nodes. Nodes are expected to play a dual role in representing their communities in RDA and promote engagement with RDA across the communities they serve. The communication and stakeholders engagement plan supports the RDA Europe Node programme during all its different phases, and namely:

- **Call launch and closure campaigns:** three different calls for new RDA Europe Nodes will be launched during the project timeframe. In the framework of WP5, this plan identifies appropriate dissemination channels to support the identification of potential new national nodes for RDA and to encourage candidates to prepare to take a formal role in supporting RDA in their country/region.
- **RDA Europe Nodes activity and outreach promotion campaigns:** European Nodes facilitate the work of RDA in many ways. They promote open calls for European participation in RDA events and initiatives, organise meetings and hands-on workshops to showcase RDA outputs to promote adoption, and lower language/cultural barriers by translating and communicating information via relevant channels. This plan ensures that proper visibility is given to each of the current and newly established Nodes and the activities that they will carry out within their mandate. The task will also make sure that the on-boarding nodes are informed about on-going activities in the network, and vice versa the network about newly joining Nodes.

The timeline below includes promotional campaigns for the communication and promotion of the RDA Europe National Nodes Network. The visualised planning in the timeline below is a living and co-created document for all WP5 project partners to work on and update from M6-M17.

Timeline 2 Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network M6 – M17

4.2.1 Campaign detailed activities

Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network	
Call launch promotional Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set-up of the grants portal (grants.rd-alliance.org) 1 Press release 1 Newsletter to the EU DB; item in RDA Global Newsletter 1 RDA European Nodes Flier Nodes starter kit & Node Group page set-up Continuous Social media campaign Support 1 webinar / call (See RDA Europe Events & webinars)
Call closure promotional activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 news piece Continuous Social media campaign
Communication activities to launch the new Nodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 press release announcing the new Nodes Nodes starter kit & Node Group page set-up 1 Article / Node / month Continuous Social media campaign 1 email to country-based RDA registered members
RDA Europe Nodes activity and outreach promotional campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 news item / event organized by a Node Email campaigns to country-based RDA registered members upon request 1 post-event report / event organized by a Node Continuous Social media campaign about Nodes events and news
Overall project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement of 13 new EU Nodes Growth rate (%) in each region covered by a European node (KPI 3.5)

Table 3 1.1 Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network detailed activities

4.3 Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals

The main objective of this promotional campaign is to increase participation and contribution of European individuals into RDA as well as the uptake and implementation of RDA results across all scientific domains. Beside the targeted promotion of the RDA value proposition for individuals and the organisation of webinars focusing on RDA for newcomers and on the opportunities for individuals at national level based on the workplans of the RDA nodes, a series of open calls for Early Careers, Experts and Ambassadors, implemented using cascading grant schemes, will be promoted.

Early career and Experts programmes: RDA Europe will build the technical expertise and knowledge base in Europe with a series of support programmes for data researchers and practitioners to facilitate participation of RDA Early Career Researchers and Experts to the RDA Plenary meetings, where they can engage directly with RDA Working and Interest Groups, learn and contribute, and become a part of the RDA global data sharing community. European experts will be sought to provide support to specific Working group maintenance or implementation. Four waves of calls will be organised, combined with RDA Plenary events.

Ambassador programme: The Ambassador Programme will create a group of domain and technical experts that are well-established in the networks of their respective domains, who can assist RDA in more deeply penetrating new and consolidated domain networks across Europe, and in turn can act as conduits for improving project support activities. Two waves of calls are expected in September-November 2018 and February-April 2019.

Experts, early careers and ambassador programme outputs promotion. Continuous promotion will be ensured to the activities performed by the grantees within their mandate. Promotion will be given, for instance, to Early Careers blogs and reports produced during Plenary meetings; to Experts' contribution to the adoption of RDA outputs via testimonials and interviews; Ambassadors will have dedicated online visibility as well as the results of the adoption projects awarded via the cascading grants.

Figure 1 RDA Europe 4.0 European open calls for individuals overview

Communication and stakeholders' engagement activities will support the RDA Cascading Grants programme during all its different phases. The timeline below includes promotional campaigns for the communication and promotion of the RDA Europe cascading grants and the activities they will carry out in their mandate. The visualised planning in the timeline below is a living and co-created document for all WP5 project partners to work on and update from M6-M17.

Timeline 3 Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals M6 – M17

4.3.1 Campaign detailed activities

Communication & promotion of RDA European call for Grants	
Call launch promotional Activities	1 Press release / call launch 1 Newsletter to the EU DB; item in RDA Global Newsletter / call launch 1 Flyer for the cascading grants programme Continuous Social media campaign
Call closure promotional activities	1 news piece / call closure Continuous Social media campaign
Communication activities to launch the grantees	1 press release announcing the awarded individuals/organizations 1 Article / grantee / month Continuous Social media campaign
Grantees activity and outreach promotional campaigns	1 blog post published by Early Career & Expert / Plenary 1 Interview / ambassador = 12 in total 1 overall RDA Europe Grants Programme booklet Continuous Social media campaign

Communication & promotion of RDA European call for Grants	
Other communication activities targeting individuals	1 flier to promote the RDA value proposition for individuals; 1 Webinars for RDA newcomers (See RDA Europe Events & webinars); 2 Webinars per year to promote the opportunities for individuals at national level (See RDA Europe Events & webinars).
Overall project KPIs	Engagement of EU Experts from at least 2 under-represented scientific domains achieved via the dedicated grants programme (KPI 2.1) Awarding of 28 grants to early career researchers and practitioners (KPI 2.2) Appointment of 12 ambassadors covering a broad range of domain communities (KPI 2.3)

Table 4 Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals detailed activities

4.4 RDA Europe Events & webinars

4.4.1 RDA Plenaries

RDA Plenaries are held every six months in different regions around the world. They are well-attended and productive events that bring together a unique community of data scientists researchers, information professionals, policymakers, funders and industry representatives. Plenary meetings are special working events that aim to move the community forward in creating tangible deliverables that improve data sharing across disciplines, technologies, and countries.

RDA Europe is responsible for supporting the organisation and the promotion of 5 RDA plenary meetings with a particular focus on the RDA plenary meetings happening in Europe. In practical terms this means communications and web support as well as supporting the organisation of the meeting, managing the breakout sessions, networking aspects as well as other visibility opportunities including poster sessions, RDA output demos, media and press partnerships.

Within this plan timeframe the following Plenaries will be organized:

- Plenary 12, 5-8 November 2018, Gaborone, Botswana, part of the International Data Week
- Plenary 13, 2-4 April 2019, Philadelphia, US

Specific contributions from RDA Europe 4.0 to Plenaries outside Europe RDA Europe 4.0 will also provide communication and dissemination support to the online presence and branding of RDA Plenaries, as part of its participation to RDA Global governance, when requested by RDA Plenary management team and by RDA Secretariat. Support in particular will include 1) the **Plenary Collocated events Call launch & organisation**, including the creation of webforms to support the call opening/closing/notification dates and the collection of necessary information from the applicants; 2) the support to all online procedures to be followed by TAB and Secretariat in **developing the schedule for Plenary events and WG/IG meetings there**, including the publication of the text call and the webform to be used for the collection of the proposals (see); 3) the support to **Plenary branding** and the design and production of **Plenary collaterals** including banners, badges, programme, posters and other graphical materials.

Overall promotion and dissemination of RDA Plenaries launch and results will be performed continuously before and after each event via all RDA communication channels.

Support will be provided for the organisation of 5 RDA Plenary meetings.

See D4.1 Updated RDA Communication Strategy for further reference

4.4.2 European Forum on GDPR

Due to the timely introduction of the new GDPR legislation, RDA Europe 4.0, as per its GA, will work on assessing the impact of GDPR and on promoting its principles and good practices worldwide. While complying with GDPR will come with time at some cost and might limit fully automatic data sharing by demanding some level of human intervention, good personal data protection should eventually help research data interoperability by building a trustful relationship between the research communities and the people offering their personal data. To facilitate adoption and knowledge sharing about the implementation and impact of the GDPR, RDA Europe 4.0 will hold a specific forum with legal and domain experts gathered from across Europe. The event will address issues arising from the EU regulation on Data Protection, (GDPR), a year following regulatory enforcement with speakers and panel discussion including GDPR officials, legal experts, examples of institutional implementation.

4.4.3 Industry events & Private Sector Involvement

Industry and the private sector's position in RDA has always been a relevant stakeholder for RDA and as such is on the radar of RDA Europe 4.0 to strengthen RDA's position in this sector, understanding which working Groups could potentially involve more private sector actors is key to RDA sustainability too. A series of industry events, involving the private sector will be organised in the project to engage more industry representatives in RDA and to explain how RDA can support them. This activity will be supported primarily by the Spanish node that has industry engagement as a focus in its national workplan.

4.4.4 Policy events

To position RDA Europe 4.0 and the overall RDA within the European policy landscape, RDA Europe will represent RDA at and contribute to several European policy events among with the EOOSC Summit, ICRI2018, the EOOSC launch event, etc. RDA will also synergise with other EU initiatives to raise awareness about RDA added value to EU Member States organising national and regional policy events (at the moment of writing this deliverable RDA Europe is in discussion with EOOSC-hub, OpenAIRE-Advance, GEANT and PRACE for support with the organisation of an event in the Balkans in 2019).

4.4.5 RDA Europe & third parties event support

RDA Europe will invest effort to obtain visibility at events organised by third-parties through keynote presentations, panel participation, co-located workshops, exhibition stand, posters, etc. This activity will increase visibility and awareness of RDA activities in the domain targeted by the event and result in increased RDA membership as well as generation of European driven RDA Working and Interest groups.

4.4.6 RDA Webinars

As already mentioned in the previous chapters, RDA Europe will organise a series of webinars focusing on RDA recommendations and outputs, RDA Europe Grants programmes, general topics related to data management, opportunities for engagement in RDA global and in activities at national level.

RDA Europe is providing communications and web support to all webinars organised, including promotion and visibility via content production, newsletters and email marketing and social media campaigns.

Timeline 4 RDA Europe Events & webinars

4.4.7 Campaign detailed activities

Stakeholders engagement events	
Event	Promotional activity
RDA plenaries (M9, M15)	Liaising with RDA global and secretariat: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly Newsletter-items announcing plenary updates • Social Media campaign on Programme, highlighting key-note speakers • Marketing materials: roll-up RDA Europe 4.0 • Communication package including RDA Cards, fliers, Adoption stories, giveaways • Continuous support for online forms and Plenary management • Continuous Social media campaign
European Forum on GDPR (M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 event Press release • 1 Newsletter to the EU community • Communication package including agenda, badges, including RDA Cards, roll-up, fliers, Adoption stories and giveaways • 1 Post event online report • Continuous Social media campaign • Live tweeting at the event

Stakeholders engagement events	
Industry events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 event Press release • 1 Newsletter to the EU community • Communication package including agenda, badges, including RDA Cards, roll-up, fliers, Adoption stories and giveaways • Social media campaign announcing workshop, highlighting key-players • 1 Post event (industry) report including next steps for RDA Europe
Policy events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Newsletter to the EU community about the RDA contribution to the policy event • 1 position paper of RDA in the EOSC and FAIR landscape • Communication package targeting EU Member States • Continuous Social media campaign
Presence at events/workshops/conferences in Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 news piece / event • Newsletter-items announcing events in EU monthly newsletters • Visibility of RDA Europe member attending, aims and outcomes in social media campaign
Webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 webinar page / webinar • 1 Newsletter-item announcing webinar in Global monthly newsletters • Visibility of RDA Europe member organising, aims and outcomes in social media campaign
Overall project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 RDA Plenaries (2 organised in Europe) • 1 Forum on Data Protection Legislation • Participation to at least 50 events (Workshops+training+meetings) in Europe (KPI5.3) • 3 industry Workshops organised • 10,000 unique monthly visitors to rd-alliance.org (KPI 4.2) • 15,000 monthly sessions to RDA global web platform on average (KPI 4.3) • 10 webinars (average attendance of at least 40 registered members per webinar) (KPI5.2)

Table 5 RDA Europe Events & webinars promotion activities

5 RDA Europe Stakeholders Analysis, communication strategy and plans

RDA Europe communication activities focus on different stakeholder groups. Each target group has its own messaging, channels, communication activities, events with associated targets, outputs and KPIs, and the nature of collaborations is tailored according to the target and the added value that RDA brings.

Many of the engagement activities will be carried out within WP2, WP3 and WP4, all supported by WP5. This section provides an outline of the stakeholders with plans on how to engage and communicate with them and includes associated KPIs for monitoring the activities and the impact.

Even though the stakeholder engagement is administratively divided into separate groups, it must be noted that the division into different stakeholder groups, and even within them, is in many cases artificial as these actors do not operate in vacuums. In the end, the results and impact of RDA activities derive from addressing various stakeholders that also have an effect on each other. Therefore, it is important to avoid silos and too narrow approaches when addressing different actors, still of course keeping in mind the specific knowledge, expertise, needs and mandate of each actor. This stakeholder analysis builds on the achievements of the previous phases of RDA Europe. The RDA Europe stakeholders are categorised in individuals, organisations and National, European & international initiatives and R&I activities and standardisation bodies. A specific mention deserves RDA global.

5.1 Individuals

Individual stakeholders are persons that because of their profession or interest can contribute to or benefit from RDA Europe 4.0. In this stakeholder category, the project identifies the data scientists and domain researchers in research communities, data providers and citizen researchers and citizens.

5.1.1 Domain researchers and Data Experts

The domain researchers are the main producers and consumers of scientific data. Better data practices in the research domain will make a significant difference in the efficiency of sharing and re-using. This stakeholder group is a very important segment for RDA. It includes many "sub-communities" working on scientific fields, and within particular institutions; interdisciplinary and cross-institutional activities are also significant. RDA Europe 4.0 addresses the domain researchers mainly through the ambassador programme.

To the category of data scientists we add data experts of several varieties: data manager, information systems specialists, and IT & technical architecture/infrastructure managers. To enable the full strength of adoption of the RDA outputs, and to take profit from latest technological insights, close collaboration with these stakeholders is crucial.

In most cases, the domain specific and cross-domain data professionals are in close interaction with each other to tackle scientific challenges. Therefore, it is important that they are addressed in a way that promotes their mutual trust and collaboration.

Engagement Objective:

- Promote the uptake of the RDA outcomes with domain researchers and data experts;
- Instigate direct interaction between RDA and individual researchers and data experts to involvement in WG & IG and disseminate RDA outcomes.

Key message & motivational mechanisms:

- RDA Europe 4.0 will provide a unique opportunity of visibility to the European Nodes and all other stakeholders who contribute to the definition of research data policies at a national or regional level.

- RDA Recommendations are developed by your fellow researchers and data experts for your use and benefit.
- Directly interacting with the RDA Europe Community, you can work in an international context to address the data challenges that you or your community is experiencing
- Working collaboratively in an international context will help build consensus, endorsement and adoption of the outputs that result, making them much more viable
- RDA Europe financially supports Early Careers and Experts to participate into plenary meeting and to contribute to RDA
- RDA Europe financially supports individuals, ambassadors and other profiles for scientific disciplines to articles official paper submissions.
- awards, special mentions, and other recognitions will be given to Organisations and Individuals who adopt any of the RDA outputs

5.1.2 Citizen scientists

Citizen scientists are the non-professionals involved in data production for scientific research. They benefit from the democratisation of science and access to scientific results as evidence of indirect investments for scientific research. The best way to attract citizen scientists' attention towards data management and its benefits, challenges and opportunities, and in general to explain the work that RDA is doing, is to link the "big data" phenomenon to those everyday challenges the general public is sensitive to, such as big societal challenges; new jobs opportunities; public investments.

Engagement Objective:

- Raising awareness of the benefits of implementing RDA's outcomes on the big societal challenges.

Key message and motivational mechanisms:

- RDA Recommendations are being developed by researchers and data experts for a proper management of "data" issues, addressing societal challenges in the earth and environmental sector, in social sciences, etc.
- The cascading grant mechanism constitutes a fundamental lever to incentivise rapid participation

5.2 Organisations

RDA Europe 4.0 will engage with target organisations during the full course of the 27-month project. RDA identifies five stakeholder organisation categories, namely funding agencies, policy makers, industry, research & academic institutes and e- & research infrastructure service and data providers.

5.2.1 Funding agencies and policy makers

RDA leverages on past investments made by member states and funding agencies for the development of research infrastructures, big data research projects, open access policies, and more. RDA Europe must act now to capture the value of past investments and demonstrate to regional agencies (e.g. European Commission and national funding agencies) the importance of further sustaining these initiatives and funding new visions and pan-European and global strategies. Benefits of engagement with RDA should also highlight the potential of greater collaboration for generating growth and jobs, as well as societal benefit of data infrastructures in furthering research into grand challenges.

This stakeholder grouping includes, among others, the following stakeholders:

- Independent EU Member/Associate States policy/advisory groups on e-Infrastructures and/or Research Infrastructures
 - e-Infrastructure Reflection Group (e-IRG)
 - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
 - G7 Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures
 - Members of the European Parliament (MEPs)

- European Commission or other EU coordinated groups
 - Research Infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) Management Committee
 - Horizon 2020 Advisory Group on Research Infrastructures
 - The Digital ERA Forum
 - Commission High Level Expert Group European Open Science Cloud
 - OSPP – Open Science Policy Platform Expert Group
 - Commission of High Level Expert Group on FAIR
- Other international groups
 - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) - Global Science Forum (GSF)
 - EIROforum Information Technology group
 - National policy actors (that are not represented in any of the stakeholders listed above)

Engagement Objectives:

- Highlighting value of RDA in Europe. Highlighting to these groups the RDA vision, the results and the benefits generated so far to the research sector and the cost effectiveness and financial benefits of continued funding.
- Intensifying and securing increased political engagement by reinforcing RDA high-level political visibility in Europe, within the European Commission itself, particularly with policy makers and organisations, initiatives and associations that will benefit from engaging with RDA to achieve their strategic, policy goals.
- Collaborate with national, regional and international groups to establish common policies for global data infrastructures for science communities and the collaboration also with e-Infrastructure groups such as EUDAT, GEANT, EGI, OpenAIRE, etc. Support and buy-in from policy groups will increase trust in open data and the creation of a registry of such policies.
- Stimulate uptake of RDA outcomes through policy making at European, national, regional and institutional level.

Key messages and motivational mechanisms:

- RDA Europe 4.0 is the reference, authoritative, global information source for Europe's effort in research data policies themes and future developments. The Early Career Programme, reinforcing knowledge around data driven policies; the Ambassadors, providing a readymade platform to disseminate their knowledge. Finally, reinforcing research priorities for post 2020 for policy, researchers, and other relevant players in the field.
- RDA Europe can help shaping the data and EU Open Science Strategy leveraging on a neutral international forum
- Become an RDA funder
- Policy makers can leverage on RDA to promote adoption and disseminate European policies within the RDA network

5.2.2 Industry, incl. Large corporations, SMEs and Start-ups/Spin-offs

Industrial engagement is of growing importance to RDA and relates to industrial players dealing with huge amounts of data, usually large companies, and to small and medium companies offering smart technologies and data services.

Engagement objectives:

- Demonstrate how RDA outputs can support industry.

Key messages and motivational mechanisms:

- RDA provides industry and the private sector with the opportunity to acquire new knowledge on data management and best practices and to develop innovative services on the basis of RDA outcomes;
- RDA helps industry to address data issues within an international neutral context;
- RDA can offer visibility to companies adopting RDA outputs.

- Become an RDA organisational member
- Awards will be given to SMEs who adopt any of the RDA outputs.

5.2.3 Research & academic institutes

Research Institutes & universities operating in different & multi disciplines domains.

Engagement objectives:

- Demonstrate how RDA can support research & academia.

Key messages and motivational mechanisms:

- RDA provides research & academic institutes with the opportunity to acquire new knowledge on data management and best practices;
- RDA supports research & academic institutes with data-related trainings;
- RDA offers to research & academic institutes an international context where to disseminate their research activities and a forum to discuss their activities with international players and experts
- Become an RDA organisational member

5.2.4 E- & Research Infrastructure service and data providers

E- Infrastructures and research infrastructures provide facilities, resources or services to research communities to conduct top-level science-related activities in all fields of science. They may encompass physical and digital components such as repositories, libraries and archives, communications networks, HPC facilities, research laboratories and equipment. Some of these infrastructures are multi-disciplinary (for example OpenAIRE or EOSC-hub, GO-FAIR network), engaging with researchers across domains, whilst others encompass broad domain areas, such as the DARIAH ERIC (Digital Research Infrastructure for Arts and Humanities), CESSDA ERIC (Digital Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences) and EPOS ERIC (European Plate Observing System). Wider research networks, such as ALLEA (the network of all European Academies), are also targets for engagement via their digital components, such as the ALLEA E-Humanities Working Group.

Engagement objectives:

- The active involvement of these stakeholders in RDA Interest and Working groups is essential, as they include scientists, data scientists, data managers, software developers and other types of professionals, focused on tackling relevant research data challenges.
- Foment the uptake of RDA's outputs by e- & research Infrastructure service and data providers.

Key messages and motivational mechanisms:

- RDA Europe 4.0 will provide a unique opportunity of visibility to the European Nodes and all other Providers who contribute to the definition of research data policies at a national or regional level.
- RDA provides e- & Research infrastructure providers a neutral forum that they can leverage on to address data issues;
- RDA provides e- & Research infrastructure providers and data providers with the opportunity to acquire new knowledge on data management and best practices;
- RDA provides e- & Research infrastructure service and data providers the potential to create new services on the basis of RDA outcomes,
- RDA provides e- & Research infrastructure service and data providers the capacity to extend their network at international level.

5.3 National, European & international initiatives and R&I activities

This stakeholder group involves all the national, European and international initiatives working in the Open Science and data-related fields and all the research and innovation activities relevant for RDA Europe. The tables below provide a batch of initiatives/R&I activities that potentially can benefit from/leverage on RDA Europe. The list of initiatives will be expanded during the project duration.

National, EU, int. R&I activities	Engagement activities & key messages
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	<p>The EOSC is one of the premier adopters of RDA outputs and RDA is ready to offer expertise and knowledge to the EOSC initiatives that are on-going or due to start in Europe by the end of 2018 onwards (e.g. EOSC-hub; OpenAIRE-Advance, FREYA, etc.). RDA Europe will liaise with the EOSC-related projects to identify potential RDA outputs relevant for their work or IGs/WGs that can support their developments.</p> <p>RDA with its over 6900 members (50% from Europe) and 25+ domain research groups is the strategic partner to represent the data community in EOSC and to achieve progress in thematic areas that need to have a global approach. RDA Europe will ensure that the RDA guidelines and recommendations are brought into EOSC via the contribution to the EOSC High Level Expert Group, to the major EOSC-related events (e.g. the EOSC Summit) and by participating to the development of the EOSC portal with the provision of relevant best practices and RDA adoption stories.</p>
European Data Initiative (EDI) & EuroHPC	<p>In the digital age, supercomputing has become an indispensable resource for fostering innovation, economic growth and social cohesion in Europe. On March 2017, seven European countries signed an agreement to start a European HPC programme that will eventually lead to European exascale supercomputers. Today around 21 countries have signed the declaration. The HPC community is a producer and consumer of big amounts of data and therefore it can largely benefit from RDA outputs and recommendations. On the other side the HPC community can also contribute to RDA itself by providing input to existing Working Groups (for example the WG on Data Security and Trust or the IG on Weather, climate and air quality). Given the existing commitment of many EU countries in the EuroHPC initiative, RDA Europe, thanks to its network of national/regional nodes will establish links with the HPC world (also leveraging on the new projects funded under the EDI initiative) to understand how the two initiatives can benefit and leverage on each other.</p>
FAIR movement	<p>Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR) data is an integral part in the process of opening up science and research. By improving the FAIR-ness of research data it will unlock the potential for both scientific research and society to draw from the benefits of this data, and also enable significant contribution to economic growth. Accordingly, the Open Science agenda contains the ambition to make FAIR data sharing the default for scientific research by 2020. RDA Europe is one of the major contributors to the FAIR movements via its several WGs/IGs. RDA Europe will ensure that the RDA recommendations and expertise are brought into the ongoing European FAIR projects and will also provide input to the Expert Group on Turning FAIR data into reality.</p>

National, EU, int. initiatives	Engagement activities & key messages
CODATA²	CODATA advocates data sharing via “policy, technological and cultural changes necessary to make research data more widely available”. It sets up committees and groups dealing with data issues around guidelines, education and training and coordination of data projects. RDA and CODATA work closely in many areas and there are several joint CODATA/RDA groups. RDA Europe will leverage the CODATA journal to promote and further disseminate the RDA outputs.
EOSC-hub³	Research Data Repository interoperability and certification, Federated Identity Management, Metadata, PIDs, Sensitive Data are only few of the areas identified by the two initiatives to advance the open & interoperable sharing of research data in Europe contributing to the EU Open Science Strategy. In addition, synergies will be established with the National Contact Points of EGI (the NGI International Liaisons – NILS) and the RDA Europe nodes to synchronise activities related to Open Science at national level and maximize the impact of both initiatives.
EOSCPilot⁴	RDA Europe can liaise with EOSC-pilot providing support to the public consultation on the Rules of Participation and promoting the RDA outputs and best practices among the EOSCpilot science demonstrators.
FREYA⁵	A strong collaboration is foreseen between the FREYA project and RDA Europe as part of the "PID Forum" of FREYA, a strong stakeholder community overseeing and influencing the development of the PID infrastructure. At this aim FREYA will contribute and leverage on the PID Interest Group and the Persistent Identification of Instruments WG. In addition, FREYA has recently launched a FREYA Ambassador Programme which aims supporting communities adopting PIDs, including ORCID and DOIs. This initiative will be leveraged by RDA Europe within its Ambassador Programme.
GO FAIR⁶	The GO FAIR Initiative will contribute to and coordinate the coherent development of the Internet of FAIR Data & Services through community-led initiatives in different activity streams. RDA Europe will synergise with the GO FAIR initiative to promote the outputs related to FAIR data coming from the RDA WG. Synergies will be also established at national level with the RDA European nodes.
INFRA-EOSC-4 2018 cluster projects	In March 2018 a set off proposals have been submitted under the INFRA-EOSC-4 2018 calls. These initiatives cover different scientific domains spanning from Neutron & Photon and Environmental Sciences to Life Science and Astrophysics. RDA Europe plans to leverage on the communities of the funded proposals (also considering other domain specific areas) to promote and collect input for its Ambassador programme.

² <http://www.codata.org>

³ www.eosc-hub.eu

⁴ www.eoscpilot.eu

⁵ www.project-freya.eu

⁶ www.go-fair.org

National, EU, int. initiatives	Engagement activities & key messages
OpenAIRE-Advance	RDA Europe and OpenAIRE-Advance share the ambition for Europe to become a global leader in digital and open science to ensure that scientists reap the full benefits of open data-driven science. RDA Europe will collaborate with OpenAIRE mainly on data management practices. In addition, synergies will be established with the National Open Access Desks (NOADs) and the RDA Europe nodes to synchronise activities related to Open Science at national level and maximize the impact of both initiatives. A set of joint webinars will be also organised.

Table 6 National, European & international initiatives and R&I activities

5.4 Standardisation bodies

This stakeholder group involves all the standardisation bodies that RDA Europe will engage to support RDA global in promoting the RDA Recommendations to faster the process of their adoption as standards.

RDA Europe 4.0 will liaise, as it has done in the past, in particular with the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP - E02758) to continue the work started in RDA Europe 3.0 to make RDA recommendations recognised as to be recognised as ICT Technical Specifications.

Among the other standardisation bodies RDA Europe will liaise with the [Internet Engineering Task Force](#)⁷ (IETF), the [World Wide Web Consortium](#) (W3C)⁸, etc.

Engagement objectives:

- RDA Europe will support RDA global to actively engage standardisation bodies to promote RDA Recommendations to get a fast track to becoming standards or to contribute to common goals and activities and overall foster adoption and build trust and engagement in new user communities.

Key messages:

- RDA recommendations can support public procurement procedures becoming ICT Technical Specifications
- RDA recommendations can contribute to the work of standard bodies.

5.5 RDA Global

As mentioned at the beginning of the document one of the main objectives of this communication plan is to ensure coordinated communication & synergies between RDA Europe 4.0 & RDA global. All the activities performed to achieve this objective are detailed in D4.1 *Updated RDA Communication Strategy*.

⁷ www.ietf.org

⁸ www.w3.org

6 Communication and Engagement tools

6.1 RDA Europe branding

The RDA Logo is registered trademark of the Research Data Alliance Foundation. To ensure consistent adherence to RDA Principles, permission is generally required to use the RDA Logo and branding. Permission is granted by the Secretary General (or designee) in consultation with the Council co-chairs. Typically, logo use is granted along with endorsement of a product or activity (see below). Detailed RDA Endorsement and Logo Usage Guidelines are available online in the RDA Communication Kit area on the RDA website (<https://rd-alliance.org/communication-kit>) and requests to use the logo are managed by RDA Secretariat via the enquiries@rd-alliance.org mailing list.

RDA Europe logo. RDA Regional logos are a replica of the RDA brand with the region indicated in blue underneath. In case of Europe, RDA Europe logo is shown below:

6.2 RDA Europe National Nodes branding

National Node branding and starter kit. In order to better engage with RDA Europe National Nodes and encourage them to act as pioneers for adoption of RDA outputs, Trust-IT created a visual identity for the current 9 EU national nodes, to be supplemented when new EU national nodes are added, to be used by the nodes in their awareness raising activities. As the national nodes are a "formal" structure under the RDA Europe grant / programme but not an officially recognised RDA global structure, the branding created for the nodes is related to the RDA Europe regional logo. The other visuals included in the visual identity created for them, distinguish them from each other.

Figure 2 Sample of RDA Europe National Node icon

National Nodes are invited to maintain a webpage within RDA national groups in RDA website where other national groups, not part of the RDA EU programme, are also listed. A **starter kit** with information materials and collaterals available for download and sharing, produced by WP5 in liaison with WP3, has been made available in all Node group pages and will be kept updated with new materials to be produced during the project timeframe. At present time the starter kit includes:

- **RDA Europe Node programme materials**
 - National node icons - for nodes websites, webpages and social media profiles
 - National nodes Handbook, available on RDA Europe owncloud repository (restricted access)

- National Nodes Flyer
- National Node ppt template – one per country
- Node folder, available on RDA Europe owncloud repository (restricted access)
- Membership country statistics, available on RDA Europe owncloud repository (restricted access)
- **RDA general materials**
 - RDA Endorsement and Logo Usage Guidelines
 - RDA in a Nutshell slidedeck - updated statistics on the RDA Membership issued on a monthly basis.
 - RDA Recommendations and Adoption cards - downloadable from RDA Communication kit
- **Documents available in country language**

The Nodes Group pages are the collaborative web space where all nodes are invited to promote their activity by posting news and publishing events within their country-based communities. They are also the main channel to directly engage with RDA country users leveraging on the activities to be performed as part of this plan by WP5, e.g. email messages (in country language) to the RDA users from that country to invite them to join the National Group page and follow the Nodes activities; promotion of events and webinars organized by the Nodes and advertised within these group pages; social media distribution and inclusion in RDA newsletters to the EU database of content published within the Group pages; and more. Customer support and user guidelines are provided to all the nodes in liaison with WP3.

The following text is pinned on the top of the official RDA EU national nodes pages to clarify the grant programme support:

RDA is an international volunteer member-based organisation and as such encourages the initiative and support of its members across the globe to animate their community on a national level. RDA Europe national node are part of the RDA Europe support programme whose aim is to interact with researchers and innovators in the local language, offering them a platform for exchange of information pertinent to the RDA and their activities and in strict compliance with RDA's guiding principles of Openness, Transparency, Consensus-based, Community driven, Harmonisation and Non-profit. The national pages should not be interpreted as an official representation of the Research Data Alliance in any country or any organisation unless this is specifically stated.

At present, 9 National Group pages are online and actively maintained by each of the current Nodes. New Groups pages will be created as new Nodes get funded by RDA Europe cascading grants mechanisms.

Figure 3 Overview of RDA National Groups & EU National Nodes on rd.alliance.org

23 JUL 2018
Pubbligate Le Nuove Call RDA Europe 4.0 Per Il Programma Cascading Grant
 By Emma Lazzeri
 Sono state recentemente pubblicate le nuove call della serie RDA Europe 4.0, il progetto che si propone di supportare la crescita della comunità di esperti e professionisti nel dominio dei dati attraverso un meccanismo di cascading grants che verranno elargite durante i 27 mesi del progetto.
 Read more Add new comment 35 reads

19 JUL 2018
Call For Papers: RDA Results On Data Science Journal
 By Emma Lazzeri
 I WG e IG di RDA potranno pubblicare i loro risultati nella special collection del Data Science Journal. I costi di pubblicazione saranno coperti dal progetto RDA Europe 4.0 per i primi 6 paper accettati. Il termine ultimo per l'invio dei contributi è il 1 Settembre 2018. Per maggiori informazioni:
 Call For Papers Data Science Journal: Special Collection On Research Data Alliance Results
 Read more Add new comment 45 reads

25 MAY 2018
Open Data For Research And Enhanced Publication
 RDA e il Nodo Italiano verranno presentati da **Donatella Castelli** (CNR-ISTI) al Workshop **Open Data for Research and Enhanced Publication**, all'interno della serie **GreyForum Series 7.1**. Per maggiori informazioni visitate il sito dell'evento:
<http://greyforum.isti.cnr.it/index.php/en/>
 CONTINUE READING

Figure 4 Sample of engagement activity & recent posts performed within one of the National Node Group pages (RDA in Italy)

6.3 RDA Europe online presence within RDA web-platform

The RDA Global Platform is an essential component of the day-to-day operations of RDA Global (www.rd-alliance.org). The web platform offers all RDA members a virtual platform to interact with RDA, disseminate information, collaborate in Working & Interest groups, and provide comments on new Working & Interest group proposals. The web platform includes a series of complex content management and workflow modules to all a scalable and long-term repository for all RDA content. This includes RDA output tracking and management, individual member management, event management and eventual payment gateways for registration fee management. Built by the RDA Europe partner Trust-IT, using the Drupal Open Source platform, it provides dedicated working areas for the RDA Working and Interest Groups, and coordination bodies. It is the main communication and dissemination channel for all RDA activities.

Trust-IT is responsible for the maintenance and upgrade effort necessary to ensure the web platform will continue to answer the needs of the RDA members, provide an enhanced user experience and foster community dialogue and exchange. The technical enhancements foreseen will be focused on the content management platform, user profiles, improved workflows, tracking and versioning. The implementation and maintenance of graphic design & branding will also be managed under this plan. It will cover the coordination and production of both RDA Global and RDA Europe 4.0 branding material and visuals.

*In June 2018 a **Roadmap** was released by Trust-IT Services, WP5 leader and website developer, and sent to RDA Secretariat providing a plan to evolve the rd-alliance.org platform to match better the needs and requirements of its growing community of users. **The Roadmap shows the route through which the RDA community can be widened by engaging new users with the introduction of appropriate marketing and communication levers during a smooth, 15-month, 3-release trajectory.** The first milestone of this Roadmap is a revamp of the look and feel of the RDA Global platform which has been published in August, 3rd 2018.*

For detailed description of the RDA Website and the Roadmap see D4.1 Updated RDA Communication Strategy

Activity	KPI for the overall project
New content items	20 per month
Unique users	10.000 unique users per month
Monthly sessions RDA Global web platform	15,000 monthly sessions
Downloads RDA outputs & recommendations.	1 flash report per month
Qualitative metrics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gender ● Discipline ● Geography ● Field of expertise 	
Profiled database with 50% EU	EU: increase with 1000 + records M12, increase 2000 + records M27

Table 7 RDA Web platform overall KPIs

6.4 RDA Europe Cascading Grants portal

A dedicated grants management web-platform has been implemented by TRUST-IT to manage in an efficient and transparent ways all the RDA Europe 4.0 cascading grants. The platform available at <https://dashboard-grants.rd-alliance.org/> has been set up and linked to the RDA global website.

The platform allows the publication of all the RDA Europe open calls, indicating which ones are open and closed, showing the description of the calls and the related evaluation criteria.

The screenshot shows the RDA Europe Cascading Grants portal. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the RDA logo, the text "RESEARCH DATA SHARING WITHOUT BARRIERS", and links for "Login | Register |" and social media icons. Below this, there are links for "OPEN CALLS", "ABOUT RDA EU 4.0", and "CONTACT". The main content area is titled "RDA Europe Cascading Grants" and includes a brief description of the RDA and its mandate. Below this, there are four call boxes, each with a "VIEW MORE" button:

- Call For External Evaluators**: Close date: 28 February 2020 - 18:00 CEST. The RDA Europe 4.0 project is seeking applications to become an external evaluator for proposals to be funded by the project. Evaluators will be responsible for evaluating applications in response to RDA Europe's open calls.
- Call For Experts**: Close date: 30 August 2018 - 17:00 CEST. RDA Europe is offering financial support to European Experts, mid-career or senior data professional / scientists: to attend 12th RDA Plenary meeting, to be held in Gaborone, Botswana 5-8 November 2018, as part of the International Data Week 2018.
- Call For Early Careers**: Close date: 30 August 2018 - 17:00 CEST. RDA Europe is offering financial support to Early Career European Researchers & Scientists working with data to attend the 12th RDA Plenary meeting, to be held in Gaborone, Botswana 5-8 November 2018, as part of the International Data Week 2018.
- Submit your proposal now and receive financial support for the set up of new national or regional nodes. Read the call text for details.** Close date: 16 August 2018 - 17:00 CEST.

At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the text: "RDA Europe 4.0 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 (H2020) research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no 777388."

In addition, the platform allows a smooth and transparent evaluation process for the selected external evaluators called to assess the Cascading Grant calls. A complete description of the platform will be provided in D1.5 Cascading Grant Report management (M27).

6.5 Communication Toolkit

The toolbox aims to ensure the timely delivery of high-quality materials and tools supporting stakeholder engagement with messages tailored to various levels of knowledge. The communication toolkit aims to align and facilitate the engagement and communication for RDA Europe 4.0 project partners, the National Nodes, the RDA Europe ambassadors and for European activities of the RDA global secretariat. The toolbox is KPI-based for communications and stakeholder engagement, as described in the following table for M6-M17 and recaps also on communication and marketing materials already listed in previous chapters related to specific promotion campaigns.

6.5.1 Content production

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Special editions of CODATA Data Science Journal focusing on RDA outputs and use cases	4 special editions CODATA Data Science Journal M1-M27
Articles specifically written for CORDIS RESEARCH EU, CORDIS Results Packs, and Digital Single Market blogs for timely information about RDA results demonstrating EU	2 CORDIS Articles per year 2 DSM blog publications per year
Press releases / articles on key milestones of RDA Europe 4.0 targeting stakeholders (policy, citizen, industry)	Minimum 2 press releases per year / up to 6 per year
Scientific paper on RDA outcomes or adoption cases	2 scientific papers / year
Packaged publication on new disciplines, nationally focused or for industry	1 packaged publication / year

Table 8 Content production KPIs

6.5.2 Flyers, Factsheets, infographics, posters, roll-ups

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Flyer for grants programme promotion	3 flyers x year with updates: -National Nodes -Grants Programme -Specific value proposition for stakeholders
Adoption stories fliers	10 new adoptions stories fliers
Infographic	2 infographics
Roll-up RDA Plenary, focusing on RDA outcomes	1 roll-up
1-pager for each RDA recommendation	
1 RDA Cards for each RDA recommendation	

Table 9 Collaterals production KPIs

6.5.3 Videos

Activity	KPI for the overall project
Short video animations on RDA Recommendations and adoption cases	12 video-animations per year
1 overall video about RDA Adoption stories	1 video

Table 10 Videos KPIs

6.5.4 Newsletters and email marketing

The RDA Europe 4.0 project will be disseminating its results through both the monthly European and Global newsletters. Direct email marketing can be used to deliver RDA communications to the +7000 members that form the RDA community, where the European Newsletter targets 50% of the entire

RDA Community at the time of writing (3570 users). Direct email marketing will be used for press-releases.

RDA newsletters are issued every month and sent to the entire RDA community of registered users. Following a rotation principle, their creation is managed by the US and the EU team.

See D4.1 Updated RDA Communication Strategy for further reference

Activity	KPI
Global Newsletter to +7000 RDA members	12 per year
European Newsletter to 50% RDA Community	6 per year
Direct email marketing to country-based communities	upon request

Table 11 Newsletters KPIs

6.6 Social Media Strategy

The Social Media strategy is designed in 5 tiers, each of them aligned with the 5 promotional and communication campaigns laid out in chapter 3:

1. Cascading grants programme
2. National Nodes
3. RDA Outcomes & recommendations
4. Events
5. RDA in general

Activity	KPI
Overall Social media connections	Start with 5,000+ overall social media followers (Twitter + LinkedIn) to 7500 in M17 and 10,000 in M27
Webinars	5 per year organized by RDA Europe; continuous support and promotion of webinars organized by RDA Global
Youtube	250 views per month 5 acquired subscriptions to the YouTube channel
Slideshare	At least 12 power point presentations uploaded about <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Nodes • RDA engagement in Plenaries • RDA engagement in other workshops and events
Twitter	10 tweets/week with RDA Global and RDA EU profiles
LinkedIn	Min. 5/month posts on LinkedIn

Table 12 Social media strategy KPIs

7 Internal Communication processes

Many of the Communication activities set out in the communication campaigns timelines are designed to increase the impact of activities carried out in all WPs of RDA Europe 4.0. The processes are thus initiated in a timely manner by all WP leaders and disseminated through a close day-to-day communication with WP5. The day-to-day communication takes place through regular online meetings of the Work Packages, Executive Board and the Governing Board to coordinate the effort and specific tasks.

WP5 team set-up a specific Coordination Group named “RDA/EU - Communication, Marketing, Impact & Sustainability” within the RDA web platform where to collaborate and monitor the activities performed within the WP. Every two weeks the WP5 team meets to define the short-term activities for each of the described campaigns. WP leaders are represented within WP5 and are responsible for asking specific communication and outreach support for their tasks. Meeting agenda and minutes are maintained by Trust-IT within the above-mentioned Drupal Group in the website.

In addition, the weekly RDA Secretariat calls are attended by the RDA WP2 and WP5 partners to ensure maximising impact of RDA Europe and RDA global efforts, while WP5 coordinator is also one of the two editors and coordinator of the RDA Global Communication plan (Sara Pittonet; see D4.1 Updated RDA Communication Strategy for further reference).

RDA/EU - Communication, Marketing, Impact & Sustainability
Home » Working And Interest Groups » Coordination Group » RDA/EU - Communication, Marketing, Impact & Sustainability

View Edit Group Outline Revisions Track Devel

Group details

Chair (s): Sara Pittonet Gaiarin
Group Email: wp5@rda-groups.org

— History —

WP5 conference calls take place every two weeks on Friday at 10:00 CEST according to the following schedule:

June	July	August	September	October	November	December
1/6	15/6	29/6	13/7	27/7	10/8	24/8
7/9	21/9	5/10	19/10	2/11	16/11	30/11
14/12	28/12					

Please always advise as soon as you know that you will not be participating in a call. Some links for collaboration are listed below:

- WP5 calls agenda and minutes
- Editorial plan
- Communication kit (incl. Nodes starter kit)
- News & events mastersheet

RDA Europe relevant social media accounts:

- Twitter: id: icordi.project@gmail.com pw:1cordi2012
- LinkedIn : Id: icordi.project@gmail.com pw:1cordi2012
- Slideshare (RDA Global LinkedIn account): id: researchdataalliance@gmail.com pw: researchdataalliance
- Google Calendar: id: rdaeu4@gmail.com - pw: rdaeu42018

RDA/EU - Communication, Marketing, Impact & Sustainability

Group Email: wp5@rda-groups.org

Private - accessible only to group members

You are the group manager

Index Add new content

Group Wiki
Group Mailing list Archive

Case Statement

Create new Case Statement

Figure 5 Overview of the WP5 Coordination Group on RDA website

An **editorial plan** is shared with all WP partners to ensure continuous and proper monitoring and planning of communication activities about all main RDA core topics and activities. A snapshot of the editorial plan is provided below:

1	Social media promotion checklist																			
2	Publication period	Partner in charge	Newsletter	News	Events	Plenaries	Webinar	RDA grants	Node focus	Recommendations & Outputs	Member Focus Content	Discipline-focus content	Org. Member Focus	Group Updates & Profile	RDA Ambassadors	Press Release & Publications	Blogs	Commits To		
3			EU focused content published in the Global Newsletter	EU news	Upcoming events or info about past events	Info about upcoming Plenary	Upcoming webinars	Info about the Nodes programme & deadlines		News from Recommendation & Outputs	If anything relevant on EU side	New published content in the section	If anything relevant on EU side	News from Groups	If anything relevant on EU side	Any new publications published	Promotion of blogs published	Promotion any new graphic materials		
4	04/05/2018	DCC			deadline for registration to the CODATA event	Call for Sessions	23 May webinar			RDA ICT Technical Specifications in Europe										
5	18/05/2018	Trust-IT	17 May Newsletter	Launch of the Nodes call	Event in Finland 5 June		Further promotion + post event dissemination	Branding guidelines										RDA Nodes call PR		
6				6th June Finland event + DMR call for papers + Open Data Research Publication & updates from Pisa event	deadline for call for sessions	Slide from the webinar + video recording	Call for evaluators + National groups pages			23 Things & its translation								Node start		
7	01/06/2018	UGOE	June Newsletter	CODATA Journal	EOSSC & FAIR consultations	EOSSC Summit - recording & materials	deadline for call for sessions	Promotion of national group pages + flier (when ready) + call for evaluators			Early careers Elli & Fots - see news by the EC		CESSDA - see Global newsletter					Call for evaluators	Early careers Elli & Fots - see news by the EC	New map f RDA Node:
8	15/06/2018	Trust-IT			CODATA journal issue - deadline for submission	LIBER event	retweet from RDA Global	recordings of the nodes webinar	Call for evaluators + National groups pages				Battelle NEON - retweet from RDA Global newsletter					Call for evaluators		New flyer f RDA EU Gr once ready
9	29/06/2018	DRI - Trust_IT	EU Newsletter	Short study RDA and the Social Sciences report - news to be created	Call for TAB nominations	National event in Greece														New flyer f RDA EU Gr once ready
10	13/07/2018	Trust-IT	July newsletter					20 July Launch Early Careers & Experts call					Battelle NEON - retweet from RDA Global newsletter					Call for evaluators		New flyer f RDA EU Gr once ready

Figure 6 WP5 shared editorial plan - snapshot

8 Conclusions

This plan has set out to consider a practical approach of mapping the number of activities laid out in the GA to different timelines, for sake of clarity and ensure that these are cross-checked against their corresponding KPIs. The main conclusions of D5.1 “Communication, Marketing & Stakeholder Engagement Plan” are:

- This document is agreed upon between all of the RDA Europe 4.0 Partners and it constitutes a pragmatic plan to deliver a series of activities to which all partners – with the different levels of effort foreseen by the RDA Europe 4.0 work plan – commit to contribute; WP5 is responsible for monitoring the execution of the activities and to ensure partners’ active contribution according to their different roles and effort in the project WPs and tasks.
- This Communication Plan document serves to develop, implement and monitor what is to be done from M7 (July 2018) until the end of Month 17 (end of July 2019);
- Concerning targets, KPIs and the planned activities, the Communication Plan is in effect a “living document”.

The second release of the Communication, Marketing & Stakeholder Engagement Plan, D5.2 will report all the activities planned between M15 and M27 and map the future activities accordingly. The second report will list any corrective or mitigated actions as a result of the planned activities here.